

**Open Research Case Study
Lancaster University**

Open Hardware as a Foundation for Accessible and Reproducible Research

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For the past several years, my work has centered on embedding open research principles into the design, dissemination, and long-term stewardship of research hardware. Although I have long been an advocate for Open Access and Open Source methodologies, my involvement in Lancaster University's Reimagining Research Practices (RRP) project^[1] has allowed me to truly scale this commitment. Within the RRP project, I have been able to develop tools, platforms, and processes that make research hardware more accessible, transparent, and reproducible, particularly for non-technical researchers who have historically been excluded from hardware-driven inquiry.

A persistent challenge in research environments is the lack of discoverability and longevity for hardware outputs. Devices are often bespoke, poorly documented, and difficult to trace across projects or departments. To address this, I developed HWIDX.org^[2,3], an open index designed to act as a persistent, citable registry for research hardware documentation. This has been taken up by the entire Devices Lab group and there has been recent interest for its use by folks at the University Library. This work directly supports transparency and reproducibility by ensuring that hardware artifacts remain findable and referenceable long after individual projects conclude.

Alongside my work to improve discoverability, maintenance and documentation remain major barriers to equitable access. Many research devices are effectively "single-use" because their documentation is inconsistent or inaccessible. To counter this, I have created a suite of documentation frameworks^[16,17,18] that enforce structural consistency and clarity. These templates underpin the open documentation for devices such as Rib:Bit^[19] and AccessBit^[20], enabling researchers; regardless of technical background, to understand, rebuild, and adapt the hardware. This approach attempts to directly address the reproducibility issues inherent with hardware-dependent research by ensuring that knowledge is not locked within specialist teams.

Much of my work builds on the Micro:bit, chosen for its accessibility, community support, and pedagogical reach across all educational levels. All associated software is released under an open-first methodology, with source code made publicly available on GitHub^[4,5,6,7,8,9,10]. This modularity facilitates a "long-tail" of utility where tools can be repurposed far beyond their initial research context and echoes my previous work with the Clip:bit and Access:bit^[11,12,13,14,15].

Even the hardware designs themselves are developed with the intention of full open release once university IP and commercial considerations are resolved. This ensures that openness is

not an afterthought but a core design principle, balanced pragmatically with institutional requirements.

A key component of equitable research is ensuring that tools reach communities beyond academia. To this end, I have proactively participated in outreach events engaging the general public, teachers and pupils, citizen scientists, and organised groups such as police and ambulance services. These engagements demonstrate that research-grade sensing, communication, and data-logging tools can be accessible to non-technical users when designed with openness and clarity in mind. They also help cultivate a culture in which research hardware is not perceived as specialist or exclusionary. A particularly significant example is the pro² network+[²⁶] Device Prototyping Summer School, an initiative that brings together designers of all experience levels and one in which I have taught since its inception[^{27,28}].

To maximise visibility and uptake, I disseminate my work across multiple platforms and formats, including ResearchGate[²¹], LinkedIn[²²], my own personal website[²³], and the project websites themselves, such as HWIDX.org.

Open hardware requires ongoing maintenance, manufacturing, and support; needs that are often overlooked in academic contexts and often relegated to company spin-out efforts. To ensure the long-term availability of these tools, I am developing commercial pathways under the umbrella of the university itself that remain aligned with open-source principles. These aim to provide a sustainable mechanism for funding ongoing upkeep, ensuring that the research outputs remain openly accessible.

Through the development of open hardware, open-source software, structured documentation, and sustainable dissemination pathways, my work aims to make research tools genuinely accessible, transparent, and reproducible both locally and internationally. By addressing systemic barriers around discoverability, documentation, and long-term stewardship, and by engaging directly with diverse communities, I am contributing to a more equitable research ecosystem; one in which hardware is not a gatekeeper but an enabler of knowledge creation.

References

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